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The Effect of Awareness Training on Fear of Surgery

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This study was conducted to determine the effect of awareness training given to patients undergoing surgical intervention on surgical fear.

Materials and Method: The study was conducted as a pre-test-post-test one-group quasi-experimental model between May 2021 and August 2021. It was conducted in the General Surgery Department of a University Hospital in eastern Turkey. The research population consists of all adult patients who will undergo surgery in the General Surgery Service of the University Hospital. The sample of the study consisted of 219 patients selected from this population by random sampling method. Personal Information Form and Surgical Fear Scale were used to collect the data. Descriptive statistics and paired t test were used in the evaluation of the data.

Results: In the study, it was found that the mean surgical fear scores of the patients decreased after the training and there was a significant difference between the total scores of surgical fear before and after the training ($p<0.05$). There was a significant difference between the mean scores of surgical fear related to short-term and long-term outcomes before and after the training ($p<0.05$).

Conclusion: Awareness training given to patients undergoing surgical intervention was found to reduce surgical fear.

Keywords: Surgical fear, awareness training, nursing.

1.INTRODUCTION

Hospitalisation for illness, diagnosis and treatment often causes negative feelings. Since they cannot fulfil their responsibilities, individuals feel dependent and their lives are affected in many ways due to reasons such as uncertainty. However, anxiety and fears of patients increase (1,2,3). Surgical interventions that cause changes in the physiological functions of the patient affect the patient negatively in terms of physiological and psychological aspects, whether they are small, large, emergency or planned in terms of risk (4,5,6). Among these negative effects, the most common fear is experienced by patients in different degrees in the preoperative and postoperative periods. The fear experienced is seen depending on the surgical interventions the patient has undergone, the personal characteristics of the patient, and reasons such as pain that may occur in the postoperative period, disruption of body integrity, and uncertainty (6,7).

In addition to the surgical technique, the education given to the patient, patient preparation in the preoperative period and quality care applied to the patient after surgery affect the success of the surgical intervention. Patient education given by healthcare personnel in the preoperative period has been reported to reduce patient fear and anxiety (1,3,4). It has been reported that patients who did not receive preoperative education experienced psychological problems before and after surgical intervention and postoperative complications increased accordingly (8,9).

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Preoperative nursing care aims to inform the patient about the surgical intervention to be performed and to prepare the patient in the best way possible for the procedures to be performed. In the literature, it has been found that it is important to inform patients about this process before the surgical intervention in order to reduce the negative effects of fear and anxiety experienced by patients in relation to surgery (5,10,11). In preoperative education, the patient should be informed about the surgical procedure, surgical team members, and the physical characteristics of the operating theatre. Talking to the patient in a relaxing way while giving education, acting in a caring and tolerant manner are among the expectations of patients from nurses in the preoperative period (1).

It is among the responsibilities of surgical nurses to complete patient preparation for surgical intervention in a good way, to prevent complications that may occur, and to provide information about the surgical process. It has an important place in reducing the fear and anxiety experienced before surgery (4,5).

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of preoperative information and awareness training about the operation and postoperative period on the level of surgical fear in patients who will undergo surgical intervention.

2.MATERIAL AND METHOD

2.1.Research model

The study was designed as a pretest-posttest one-group quasi-experimental model. This study was conducted in the General Surgery Service of the University Hospital between May 2021 and August 2021. The population of the study consisted of all adult patients who will undergo surgery in the surgical service. The sample size was determined by G Power 3.1.9.7 programme (12). According to the 0.7% effect size, 0.05 margin of error, 0.95% confidence interval, and 95% power analysis with 95% power to represent the population, 230 patients were determined. The sample included patients who met the inclusion criteria and were selected from the population by random sampling method. Nine patients who did not meet the inclusion criteria and 2 patients who did not accept to participate in the study were excluded from the study, and the study was completed with 219 patients.

The research data were collected by the researcher from all adult patients who were hospitalised in the surgical ward for at least 48 hours by face-to-face interview technique in patient rooms. Inclusion criteria: voluntary participation in the study, being an adult, not having any communication problem, not being diagnosed with psychiatric disease. Patients from whom permission to participate in the study could not be obtained and patients who did not fulfil the inclusion criteria were excluded from the study.

2.2. Data collection

Personal Information Form and Surgical Fear Scale were administered to the patients as pre-test before the operation. The patient was educated about the surgical intervention to be performed. After the patient education, the Surgical Fear Scale was applied as a post-test.

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Data collection in the study; In the first stage, which started with the hospitalisation of the patients before surgical intervention, the patients were informed about the study and their written and verbal permissions were obtained for their participation in the study. All patients who agreed to participate in the study were administered the Personal Information Form and Surgical Fear Scale as a pretest on the day before the surgical intervention. The responses of the patients were recorded by the researcher.

Awareness training given to patients before surgical intervention; preoperative waiting and postoperative recovery units, operating room, tables with surgical instruments, sterile drapes, surgical team members, as well as information to be obtained from the patients themselves when going to the operating theatre, positions to be given for surgical intervention and precautions to be taken, communication methods to be provided with patient relatives during surgery, interventions in the postoperative recovery unit and criteria for being sent to the ward. This information was given verbally by the researcher. All interviews and information were conducted in surgical wards, in the patients' rooms and by providing a suitable interview environment. This interview lasted approximately 30 minutes.

In the second stage of the data collection process, before the patients were sent from the ward to the operating theatre, the researcher asked the patients to answer the questions in the surgical fear scale again as a post-test, this interview lasted approximately 10 minutes. The research data were collected using the Personal Information Form and Surgical Fear Scale.

2.2.1. Personal Information Form: The form, which reports the sociodemographic characteristics and health status of the patients, was created by the researcher in line with the literature (9,10).

2.2.2. Surgical Fear Scale (SFS): It was developed by Theunissen et al. (13) to evaluate the fear levels of patients who would undergo surgical intervention, and its validity and reliability study was performed by Bağdigen and Özlü (14). The scale consists of 8 items with a numerical scale between 0-10. This scale, which consists of two sub-dimensions, shows the fear of short and long-term consequences of surgical intervention. Items 1-4 in the scale measure the fear of short-term consequences of surgical intervention, while items 5-8 measure the fear of long-term consequences of surgical intervention. The lowest score that can be obtained from the scale is 0 and the highest score is 80. High scores obtained from the surgical fear scale indicate high levels of fear. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the scale is 0.76-0.92 for the original scale. For this study, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the scale was found to be 0.96.

2.3. Data analysis

The data obtained in the study were analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Science 22.00 (SPSS) statistical package programme. Shapiro-Wilk normality analysis was applied to determine the suitability of the measured parameters for normal distribution. All of the measured parameters were found to be suitable for normal distribution. In the evaluation of the obtained data, percentage, mean, standard deviation and paired t test statistical calculation method were used as descriptive statistical methods. The data were analysed at 95% confidence interval and $p < 0.05$ (15).

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2.4. Ethical aspects of the research

Permission was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the University (decision no: 2021/05 - 28) to conduct the research. All participants voluntarily participated in the study. The purpose of the study was explained by the researchers and informed signed consent was obtained from those who agreed to participate in the study. To those who voluntarily participated in the research; the researchers undertook that all information would be kept confidential, the data obtained would be used only for research purposes and that they could withdraw from the research at any time. The research was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

3. RESULTS

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to demographic characteristics (n=219)

Characteristics	n	%
Age (mean ± SD)	38.11±8.4 (min:25.00, max:69.00)	
Gender		
Female	103	47.0
Male	116	53.0
Profession		
Unemployed	11	5.0
Housewife	59	26.9
Civil servant	58	26.5
Retired	66	15.1
Labourer	49	8.7
Self-employment	39	17.8
Marital Status		
Married	162	74.0
Single	57	26.0
Education Status		
Illiterate	32	14.6
Primary school	35	16.0
Secondary school	26	11.9
High school	53	24.2
University	73	33.3
Previous surgery status		
Yes	140	63.9
No	79	36.1
Presence of chronic disease		
Yes	78	35.6
No	141	64.4

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The mean age of the patients who participated in the study was 38.11 ± 8.4 years. It was observed that 53% of the patients were male, 26.9% were housewives, 74% were married and 24.2% were high school graduates. It was found that 63.9% of the patients had undergone surgery before and 64.4% had no chronic disease (Table 1).

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to their informed status regarding the surgical process (n=219)

Characteristics	n	%
Information on the Preoperative Period		
-No information given	82	37.4
-Informed by the nurse	47	21.5
-Informed by the doctor	90	41.1
Informed about the Intraoperative Period		
- No information given	111	50.7
- Informed by the nurse	60	27.4
- Informed by the doctor	48	21.9
Informed about the Postoperative Period		
- No information given	85	38.8
- Informed by the nurse	49	22.4
-Informed by the doctor	85	38.8

It was found that 41.1% of the patients who were informed in the preoperative period were informed by the doctor, 27.4% of the patients who were informed in the intraoperative period were informed by the nurse, and 38.8% of the patients were informed by the doctors in the postoperative period (Table 2).

Table 3: Comparison of Surgical Fear Before and After Training

SCALE	Pre-training Mean \pm SD	Post-training Mean \pm SD	T test	p
Fear of Surgery	44.67 \pm 19.96	33.87 \pm 17.63	19.747	0.001
Short-term results				
Fear of surgery	22.54 \pm 10.16	17.37 \pm 8.98	12.412	0.001
Long-term results				
Fear of surgery	22.12 \pm 10.50	16.50 \pm 9.31	18.696	0.001

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In the study, while the total mean score of the surgical fear scale was 44.67 ± 19.96 before the training, the total mean score decreased to 33.87 ± 17.63 after the training, and there was a significant difference between the total scores of the surgical fear scale before and after the training ($p < 0.05$). A significant difference was found between the mean scores of the surgical fear sub-dimension related to short-term consequences before and after the training ($p < 0.05$). A significant difference was found between the mean scores of the surgical fear sub-dimension related to long-term outcomes before and after the training ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3).

4. DISCUSSION

Although there are treatment interventions aiming to protect and improve the patient's life, all surgical interventions are perceived by the patient as life-threatening and frightening practices. The stress created by this perception causes a physiological and psychological response in the body. From the diagnosis of the disease, the decision for surgical intervention and hospitalisation increases the patient's fear and anxiety level. This fear experienced by the patient may lead to delay in wound healing after surgical intervention, prolonged discharge time, prolonged treatment time and problems in compliance with treatment (16). Therefore, surgical fear should be evaluated in the preoperative period and patients should be informed about the surgical process.

In the study, while the total mean score of the surgical fear scale was 44.67 ± 19.96 before the training, the total mean score decreased to 33.87 ± 17.63 after the training, and there was a significant difference between the total scores of the surgical fear scale before and after the training ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3). Lee et al. In a study conducted with patients undergoing spinal surgery, anxiety was found to be significantly lower in the intervention group that received training (10). Kaya and Özlü reported that the level of surgical fear was 37.55 ± 21.11 in their study with patients undergoing elective surgical intervention (16). Marsy reported that preoperative surgical fear was high in his study (17). In the study, a significant difference was found between the mean scores of the surgical fear sub-dimension related to short- and long-term results before and after the training ($p < 0.05$). Kaya and Özlü reported that the level of fear related to short-term consequences of surgical intervention was 18.03 ± 11.44 and the level of fear related to long-term consequences of surgical intervention was 19.52 ± 11.87 (16).

5. CONCLUSION

It was found that fear of surgery decreased with preoperative education. It is thought to be useful in reducing the negative effects of surgical fear, accelerating wound healing and reducing surgical complications by reducing the existing fear with nursing interventions.

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